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MetaOS Project

Data-Driven Cognitive Production: Revolutionising Industry 4.0 with Modular Manufacturing Systems

Background

In today's rapidly evolving manufacturing landscape, the demand for highly flexible, sustainable, and smart production lines is increasing. Companies require strategies for mass customisation to process a wide range of products while ensuring efficiency, sustainability, and adaptability. The deployment and validation of cognitive production processes are essential to meet these demands, enabling intelligent, autonomous decision-making and self-optimization.

The Company

The use case focuses on implementing MAL4 cognitive production processes across four public-private Pilot Lines (PL) located at prestigious facilities: [INNO Didactic Factory](#) at AIC in Bilbao, Spain; [MADE Competence Centre](#) & [POLIMI Industry 4.0 Lab](#) in Milano, Italy; [SSF open factory lab at SIPBB](#) in Biel, Switzerland; and [SIEMENS INNOVATION CAMPUS](#) in Nuremberg, Germany. These sites collectively offer 5000 m2 of cutting-edge Industry 4.0 production systems and host over 500 companies.

The Needs

The evolution of existing modular manufacturing systems necessitates strategies for mass customisation to handle a diverse product range. There is a need for highly flexible, sustainable, modular digital production lines capable of manufacturing new products in low-volume production. This requires smart rapid response features, self-optimization, reconfigurations, and adaptation of the production line. Fast data processing is crucial to enable intelligent, human-centred decisions, augmented and assisted by technology.

The solution

The proposed solution involves the implementation of aerOS, which introduces autonomous, flexible edge layer services with intelligent orchestration. This distributed edge-powered modular approach facilitates IoT edge-cloud continuity and modular green production orchestration services. It supports digitalising AI/

ML workflows, tactile Zero Defect Manufacturing (ZDM) control, real-time closed-loop processes, active energy monitoring, and self-adaptive scheduling.

Figure 1. – Siemens AGV's arena

Figure 2. Setup of Siemens adaptation to aerOS

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Figure 3. Task allocator

The Challenge

The primary challenge lies in integrating and optimising the diverse infrastructure and technology across the four Pilot Lines. Each site has advanced facilities, including cutting-edge stamping, machining, control, in-line verification equipment, autonomous logistics, green manufacturing concepts, and state-of-the-art automation capabilities. Ensuring seamless interaction, data integrity, security, and effective orchestration across these diverse systems is a significant hurdle. Additionally, the integration of cloud, edge, and IoT technologies adds another layer of complexity, as these systems must work cohesively to provide real-time data processing, analytics, and autonomous decision-making. Balancing the computational load between cloud and edge environments while maintaining secure and efficient data flow across IoT devices is essential for the success of the project.

The Project Involved

The EU-funded aerOS project aims to enhance the infrastructure supporting edge-to-cloud and edge computing by developing a unified meta-operating system based on a collaborative IoT-edge-cloud architecture. This system will enable flexible deployment of applications and

innovations leveraging AI, machine learning, and Big Data analytics, offering numerous benefits. The project's goal is to create a more efficient and sustainable digital infrastructure to support the ongoing growth of edge-to-cloud and edge computing.

The service provider

Siemens, a global leader in automation and digitalisation, provides the essential technology and expertise for this project. Siemens' contributions include the service allocation algorithm in aerOS, the SIMATIC Industrial edge apps, and the advanced machine learning models for orchestration. Collaboration with other renowned institutions and competence centres ensures a comprehensive and robust solution.

Impact

The implementation of aerOS across the Pilot Lines is set to achieve several significant impacts:

- ▶ Establishment of the world's first Level 4 autonomous production line with an open modular edge orchestration approach.
- ▶ Enhanced quality, circularity, and zero-footprint manufacturing processes.
- ▶ Improved data distribution and security, ensuring data integrity closer to the source.

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- ▶ Safe human-machine collaboration and dynamic intralogistics adaptation.
- ▶ Autonomous production scheduling, reducing downtime and increasing efficiency.

Future Developments

Future developments will focus on expanding aerOS's capabilities and integrating more advanced AI/ML models for continuous improvement. The project aims to explore further scenarios, such as green manufacturing with zero net energy and CO2 footprint monitoring, advanced ZDM approaches for the automotive sector, and AGV swarm intelligence for lot-size-1 production. Continuous innovation and collaboration will drive the evolution of smart, sustainable manufacturing systems.

Recommendations for policymaking

To support the widespread adoption of cognitive production processes, policymakers should consider the following recommendations:

- ▶ **Incentives for Innovation:** provide grants and tax incentives for companies investing in advanced manufacturing technologies and green production systems.
- ▶ **Standardisation:** develop and promote industry-wide standards for IoT, AI/ML, and edge-cloud integration to ensure interoperability and security.
- ▶ **Workforce Development:** invest in education and training programs to equip the workforce with the necessary skills for operating and maintaining advanced production systems.
- ▶ **Research and Development Support:** fund research initiatives focused on the development of autonomous, flexible, and sustainable manufacturing technologies.
- ▶ **Collaboration and Partnerships:** encourage public-private partnerships to foster innovation and accelerate the implementation of cutting-edge solutions in the manufacturing sector.

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- ▶ aerOS: Official website: aeros-project.eu ;
- ▶ Follow <https://www.linkedin.com>
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